

A MATHEMATICAL MODEL AND PERFORMANCE OF LASER BEAM MACHINING PARAMETERS FOR AUSTENITIC STAINLESS STEEL

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Abstract: Laser Beam Machining (LBM) is a high-precision, non-contact material removal process that offers exceptional adaptability and control, especially suited for advanced manufacturing applications. This study investigates the micromachining behavior of Austenitic Stainless Steel (316L) using a pulsed fiber laser to develop a mathematical model that correlates key process parameters, laser power, laser scanning speed, and laser line distance, with machining performance. The primary research question addresses how these parameters influence both process efficiency, represented by material removal rate (MRR), machining time, and product quality, measured through surface roughness, lattice strain, and residual stresses. A series of controlled experiments was conducted in which the parameters above were systematically varied, and the machined surfaces were analyzed using a laser confocal microscope and X-ray diffraction techniques. Regression analysis and response surface methodology were employed to derive predictive equations that model the relationships between input settings and output responses. The results indicate that laser power and scanning speed are the dominant factors influencing MRR and surface finish, while line distance plays a moderate yet significant role. The developed model exhibited high predictive accuracy ($R^2 > 96.31\%$) across both efficiency and quality metrics, highlighting its robustness. Interaction effects between parameters were also found to be statistically significant, emphasizing the need for multi-variable optimization. This mathematical framework offers valuable insights into process control and optimization, enabling manufacturers to fine-tune LBM operations for enhanced precision and repeatability. The study contributes to the broader field of laser micromachining by providing a validated predictive tool tailored to 316L stainless steel applications.

Keywords: Laser Beam Machining, Micromachining, Austenitic Stainless Steel (316L), material removal rate (MRR), surface roughness (R_a), Residual stresses.

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern manufacturing, lasers are recognized as versatile tools that enable non-contact machining of different materials, with high accuracy at micron-scale resolution, via remote control and safe operation. All these outstanding features mean that laser-based processes are capable of competing with many conventional processes, such as mechanical cutting, drilling, and milling. With special marking, engraving, or surface texturing capabilities, Laser is a widely applicable machining tool. In reality,

however, machining output, process quality, and overall cost are the key drivers that determine whether the process is cost-effective and can be industrially applied [1]. One of the most medically approved materials for several medical implants, including orthopedic implants, is AISI 316L stainless steel. Stainless steel 316L is widely used in the biomedical field, especially for manufacturing medical implants, due to its excellent biocompatibility, corrosion resistance, and mechanical properties [2]. However, producing intricate and precise surface features is critical to

ensure implant performance, such as improved osseointegration, wear resistance, and reduced bacterial adhesion [3]. Traditional manufacturing techniques often struggle to achieve the desired surface characteristics, especially when dealing with complex geometries and small dimensions inherent to implants.

Laser micromachining has emerged as a promising post-processing technique to address these challenges. It is a non-contact, high-precision process that uses focused laser beams to remove material at a micro-scale, as shown in Figure 1 [4]. This technique offers several advantages, including firstly (High precision). It can produce micro-features (grooves, micro-spots, and micro-milling) with high accuracy, crucial for the complex designs of medical implants [5]. Secondly, Minimal thermal effects with proper selection of laser parameters,

minimal thermal effects can minimize localized heat-affected zones can be minimized, preserving the metallurgical properties of stainless steel 316L [6]. Thirdly, the Versatility of Laser micromachining can be used to create a variety of surface textures and different patterns, to enhance the implant's surface characteristics [7].

Given its capability to modify surface topography and enhance functional properties without compromising the bulk material, laser micromachining can be used for biomedical implant to make rough surfaces to enhance adhesion between implant and bones or make micromachining for micro grooves to enhance the fixation strength by allowing the bone tissues to grow on these grooves during bone implantation, which might reduce surgery complexity [8].

Figure 1. Schematic of Nanosecond fiber laser system setup for Micromachining [4]

Laser-based processes have become increasingly established in the field of microtechnology due to their numerous advantages, such as high precision, flexibility, and non-contact nature. These capabilities have led to widespread applications in industries such as automotive, aerospace, and microelectronics. Common laser applications include marking, drilling, micromilling, cutting, engraving, welding, and thermal treatments, such as hardening. In particular, laser engraving is frequently employed to produce cavities in molds and dies. Deep cavities are typically achieved through multiple laser passes over the material surface, making the number of passes or scan repetitions a critical control parameter due to its direct influence on heat input and material removal depth [9].

Numerous studies have explored laser-assisted machining techniques, primarily focusing on how various process parameters affect surface roughness and machining efficiency. However, relatively limited research has addressed the laser engraving of austenitic stainless steels, especially using advanced systems such as pulsed fiber lasers.

Yasa, for instance, investigated selective laser erosion of AISI 1045 steel using a laser, examining the influence of scan overlap, pulse overlap, and other parameters on surface roughness [10]. Their results highlighted the significance of laser settings in minimizing surface irregularities. Wendland conducted experiments on deep laser engraving of aluminum alloy 5251 and stainless steel 316, emphasizing process optimization for high material removal rates and surface integrity [11]. Similarly,

Campanelli applied a Design of Experiments (DOE) approach to study the effects of parameters such as scan speed, frequency, power, and scan strategy on surface finish and material removal depth [12].

Further contributions include Pham's experimental investigations on ceramic materials, which assessed how factors like frequency, scan speed, pulse duration, and wavelength affect outcomes such as surface finish, aspect ratio, and minimum feature size [13]. Their studies confirmed that both machining accuracy and surface quality are highly dependent on laser-material interaction and pulse characteristics [14]. Leone extended this research to wood-based materials, exploring the role of pulse frequency, beam speed, and scan repetitions using a Q-switched Nd: YAG green laser ($\lambda = 532$ nm). The results showed that engraved depth is strongly influenced by mean power and scanning parameters [15].

Chen employed the Taguchi method to study the effect of five key parameters—beam expansion ratio, focal length, average power, pulse repetition rate, and engraving speed on engraving line width using a Q-switched laser system [16].

Despite these extensive efforts, there remains a clear gap in research concerning laser micromachining of stainless steel 316L, a material commonly used for medical implants. Given the critical nature of such applications, particularly in enhancing implant surface characteristics for better achieving medical function, it is essential to establish statistically robust models to optimize the micromachining process.

This study employs Response Surface Methodology (RSM) to statistically analyze experimental data and identify optimal process parameter settings. Key output responses include material removal rate (MRR), surface roughness (Ra), machining time, and lattice strain. A Box-Behnken Design (BBD) is utilized to evaluate the interactions between parameters and track variations in laser processing behavior [17].

The overarching objective of this research is to improve the functional performance of medical implants by optimizing laser micromachining factors. Specific applications include the fabrication of micro-grooves or the surface modification of medical implants to enhance their function in the human body. This work demonstrates how fiber laser micromachining can be effectively applied to meet stringent medical device design requirements by utilizing a mathematical model to optimize laser machining parameters and evaluate process efficiency and product quality.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

As a Bio-compatible material, stainless steel 316L Plate with 3 mm thickness is used for conducting the experimental study, as shown in Table 1. The experiment involves machining square sections with dimensions of 7 mm x 7 mm on the surface of AISI 316L stainless steel Plates through a 50 W (average power) MOPA pulsed fiber laser machine developed by Raycus Fiber Laser Technology, Wuhan, China. The technical specifications of this machine are listed in Table 2.

Table 1: Average chemical composition of stainless steel 316L determined with spectroscopy.

Element	C	Cr	Ni	Mn	Si	Mo	Co
Amount in Weight%	0.06	17.38	9.56	1.47	0.56	2.11	0.15

Table 2: Technical specifications of the fiber laser machine.

Machine specification	Value
Nominal average output power	50 W
Output power adjustment range	From 0 to 100 %
Pulse repetition rate	20 to 1000 KHz
Wavelength	1064 nm
The diameter of the beam	7.5 mm
Spot diameter	25 μ m
Pulse duration	100 ns
Focal length	110 mm
Axis travel (X, Y)	100*100 mm

The primary aim of this study is to identify and analyze the key process parameters in fiber laser micromachining that significantly influence the machining performance of stainless steel 316L. The investigation focuses on establishing a predictive

model that correlates laser machining parameters with quality indicators such as Material Removal Rate (MRR), surface roughness, machining time, and lattice strain. A structured experimental design was adopted to systematically evaluate the effect of

varying input parameters on these critical performance metrics.

To achieve a statistically robust analysis, the study integrates Design of Experiments (DOE) with Response Surface Methodology (RSM). RSM is particularly effective for optimizing processes involving multiple quantitative factors and is well-suited for developing empirical models based on experimental data. As described by Myers and Montgomery [18], RSM facilitates the modeling and optimization of response variables through a sequential, data-driven approach that explores factor interactions and nonlinear behavior in complex engineering systems.

Among several available experimental designs for constructing response surfaces, including three-level factorial designs, Central Composite Designs (CCD), and the Doehlert design, the Box-Behnken Design (BBD) was selected for this research [19]. BBD offers several advantages, particularly for processes with constrained experimental ranges and when minimizing the number of experimental runs is essential. One of its most notable features is the strategic avoidance of extreme factor combinations, where all variables are simultaneously at their highest or lowest levels. This characteristic makes BBD safer and more efficient, as it reduces the likelihood of damaging the material or equipment under harsh conditions [20][21].

Additionally, BBD provides sufficient data to model quadratic relationships and capture interactions between variables, making it an optimal choice for laser machining applications where precision and repeatability are critical [22]. Its focus on the central region of the parameter space enables accurate prediction of process behavior, which is particularly beneficial for the micromachining of biomedical-grade stainless steel, where surface integrity and dimensional control are paramount.

Based on preliminary trials and literature review, three key process parameters were selected for the investigation: laser power (A), laser scanning speed (B), and laser line distance (C). The low, middle, and high levels of each variable were labeled as shown in Table 3. The variables are coded by the experiments at different level settings of laser power, laser scanning speed, and laser line distance. The laser beam power is depicted as 60%, 80%, and 100% representing 28.7, 39.3, and 51.7W average power, respectively, measured by a laser power meter. The laser scanning speed is set at 500, 2750, and 5000 mm/sec, and the laser scanning distance is set at 10 μ m, 15 μ m, and 20 μ m. Other input parameters, such as pulse duration, pulse repetition rate, gas pressure (Nitrogen gas), number of scanning layers, and focal plane position (FPP) are fixed at 14 ns, 1000 KHz, 1.5 Bar, 40 times, and zero (0), respectively.

Table 3: Input factor level settings.

Symbols	Factors	Unit	Level-1	Level-2	Level-3
A	Laser Power	%	60	80	100
B	Laser scanning speed	mm/sec	500	2750	5000
C	Laser line distance	μ m	10	15	20

In this investigation, laser power, laser scanning speed, and laser line distance were selected as the primary input parameters, while Metal Removal Rate (MRR), surface roughness, Machining time, and lattice strain were used as output response variables to assess machining quality and process efficiency. DOE facilitates the examination of all potential interactions and combinations among these variables, providing a robust basis for optimization [23].

To evaluate the significance of the experimental results, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to a reduced model for each response factor. The p-value derived from ANOVA helps in testing the statistical hypothesis regarding each parameter's effect on the outputs. If the p-value is below the predefined significance level, the effect is considered statistically significant [23]. A non-significant lack of fit indicates that the model adequately represents the actual data and successfully captures the

functional relationship between input and output variables.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) quantifies how closely the predicted results align with actual observations, serving as an indicator of the model's explanatory power [24]. The adequate precision ratio representing the signal-to-noise ratio is another key metric used to confirm that the model provides sufficient sensitivity in navigating the design space [25].

The experimental runs are conducted in line with the design matrix provided by the Design Expert software, which is listed in Table 4 based on BBD. As stated previously, three laser parameters consisting of laser scanning speed, laser power, and laser scanning distance are considered process variables for stainless steel 316L material with 3 mm thicknesses. From the range available for these parameters, the numbers of levels are kept three. The MRR after laser micromachining of all the samples

is quantified by measuring the weight loss in certain time with given density ($\rho= 8 \text{ g/cm}^3$) from Equation 1. The machining Temperature is measured from the Thermal camera. In addition to the surface roughness measured by ZEISS LSM 700 laser confocal microscope. The lattice strain percentage measured from analysis X-Ray Diffraction through X'Pert High Score Plus software. The Residual stresses measured by the X-ray diffraction (XRD) $\sin^2\psi$ method. Energy density and power density evolved on the material surface is related to the laser beam's average power, which further depends upon these parameters and is calculated from Equations (2, 3, 4, and, 5).

$$MRR (mm^3/min) = \frac{Mass\ Loss/\rho (mm^2)}{Machining\ Time (min)} \quad (1)$$

$$Energy\ per\ pulse (J) = \frac{Power(W)}{Pulse\ repetition\ rate (Hz)} \quad (2)$$

$$Energy\ density\ per\ pulse (J/mm^2) = \frac{Energy\ per\ pulse(J)}{spot\ area(mm^2)} \quad (3)$$

$$Energy\ density (J/mm^2) = \frac{Energy\ density\ per\ pulse (J/mm^2)}{Speed\ factor \times Overlap\ factor \times Count\ factor} \quad (4)$$

$$Power\ density (W/mm^2) = \frac{Energy\ density (J/mm^2)}{Machining\ Time (sec)} \quad (5)$$

Speed factor: Describe the overlap of sequentially pulsed spots in terms of the scanning speed (Pulse repetition rate = 1000 kHz and spot diameter = 25 μm)

Overlap factor: Describe the adjacent pulses overlap in terms of laser line distance (spot diameter 25 μm)

Count factor: Describe the Number of scanning layers.

Table 4: Experiment design for 13 samples.

No.	A	B	C
1	60	2750	10
2	60	2750	20
3	60	500	15
4	60	5000	15
5	80	2750	15
6	80	5000	10

7	80	5000	20
8	80	500	10
9	80	500	20
10	100	500	15
11	100	2750	20
12	100	2750	10
13	100	5000	15

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

During laser micromachining, several parameters can affect product surface quality; therefore, it is very important to determine pre predominant parameter and its limits (two extremes) on machining quality represented in output different responses. In this research work, 13 specimens are machined, having dimensions of 7 X 7 mm with a 3 mm thickness of stainless steel 316L as shown in Figure 2. Table 5 contains the three main parameters of laser machining process such as consumed laser power in %, laser scanning speed in mm/sec, and laser line distance in microns. Because the relationship between those controlling parameters is complicated, it was essential to use the Design Expert software to construct a mathematical model that represented the different relationships between three main parameters and different responses, which indicate machining quality. Different responses that express laser machining parameters are energy density, power density, and Machining temperature. For quality responses, MRR, Machining time, surface roughness (Ra), and Lattice strain. To measure each response and to analyze it, Design Expert software is used. Model significance tests for every model term and the lack of fit test are carried out. A stepwise regression method is performed to formulate the significant terms. Using ANOVA tables, reduced model summaries are developed for each response. RSM is applied to perform the quality-based investigation [26]. Experiments are designed based on the three levels of BBD with complete replication. Table 5 shows those three parameters (Variables) on the left-hand side, while the other column represents different responses such as material removal rate (MRR), surface roughness (Ra), machining time, and lattice strain. Table 6 clarifies different limits (i.e., Max. & Min. limits).

Figure 2. 13 samples with parameters of the Experiment design.

Table 5: Experiment Response results.

No.	Laser parameters			Dependent parameters			Responses			
	Power	speed	distance	Energy Density (J/mm ²)	Power Density (W/mm ²)	Temp. (°C)	MRR (mg/min)	Machining Time (min)	Ra (µm)	Lattice strain (%)
1	60	2750	10	106.262	1.40187	449.5	0.395778	1.26333	7.515	0.26175
2	60	2750	20	53.1311	1.39635	444.2	0.453351	0.634167	13.528	0.2465
3	60	500	15	388.108	1.46345	469.3	0.234729	4.42	35.944	0.3075
4	60	5000	15	38.8108	1.3337	400.3	0.0515464	0.485	18.246	0.290333
5	80	2750	15	96.6325	1.91352	506.1	0.80198	0.841667	20.256	0.2855
6	80	5000	10	80.05	1.83601	445.7	0.774083	0.726667	12.519	0.330667
7	80	5000	20	40.025	1.82763	417.1	0.821918	0.365	16.434	0.28175
8	80	500	10	800.5	2.01282	608.6	0.501634	6.62833	71.179	0.3015
9	80	500	20	400.25	2.00727	572.5	0.364845	3.32333	91.249	0.326143
10	100	500	15	699.192	2.63647	647.7	0.469457	4.42	95.162	0.4
11	100	2750	20	95.7177	2.51558	482.9	0.906702	0.634167	46.772	0.288667
12	100	2750	10	191.435	2.52553	582.3	0.811346	1.26333	28.681	0.31575
13	100	5000	15	69.9192	2.40272	533.8	1.03093	0.485	13.604	0.294

Table 6: Maximum and minimum values chosen for different parameters

Symbol	Parameter	Unit	Min. Value	Max. Value
A	Laser power	(%) Watt	(60%) 28.7	(100%) 51.7
B	Scanning speed	mm/sec	500	5000
C	Laser line distance	µm	10	20

3.1. ANOVA and Regression Modelling

The responses, including material removal rate (MRR), surface roughness (Ra), machining time, and

lattice strain, were analyzed by generating an ANOVA table. the results of the ANOVA test were used to determine the statistical significance and

effect of process factors on performance measures [27].

a) Material Removal Rate (MRR)

Material Removal Rate (MRR) in laser micro-machining refers to the volume of material removed per unit time during the laser processing of a workpiece. According to Table 4, an ANOVA was generated using Design Expert software to determine the significant and insignificant parameters affecting MRR statistically. According to Table 7, which displays the ANOVA for MRR. The model F-value of 13.06 indicates that the model is significant. There is only a 1.26% probability that an F-value this large will occur owing to noise. P-values of less than 0.0500 suggest that model terms are significant.

Significant model terms are A, B, AB, A², and B². Values above 0.1000 imply that the model terms are not significant. The final regression equation for the MRR model is presented in Equation 6 (in terms of actual factors).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{MRR} = & -2.18598 \\
 & +0.066805 \text{ power} \\
 & -0.000122 \text{ Scanning speed} \\
 & -0.017240 \text{ laser line distance} \\
 & +4.13696\text{E-}06 \text{ power * Scanning speed} \\
 & +0.000094 \text{ power * laser line distance} \\
 & +4.10278\text{E-}06 \text{ Scanning speed * laser line distance} \\
 & -0.000416 \text{ power}^2 \\
 & -3.80492\text{E-}08 \text{ Scanning speed}^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Table 7: ANOVA for MRR.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	0.984	8	0.123	13.06	0.0126	significant
A-power	0.5424	1	0.5424	57.59	0.0016	
B-Scanning speed	0.1534	1	0.1534	16.29	0.0157	
C-laser line distance	0.0005	1	0.0005	0.0543	0.8272	
AB	0.1386	1	0.1386	14.72	0.0185	
AC	0.0004	1	0.0004	0.0379	0.8551	
BC	0.0085	1	0.0085	0.9048	0.3954	
A²	0.0776	1	0.0776	8.24	0.0455	
B²	0.1039	1	0.1039	11.03	0.0293	
Residual	0.0377	4	0.0094			
Cor Total	1.02	12				

b) Surface Roughness (Ra)

Table 9 displays the ANOVA for Ra. The Model F-value of 25.34 indicates that the model is significant. There is only a 1.12% probability that an F-value this large will occur owing to noise. P-values of less than 0.0500 suggest that model terms are significant. A, B, AB, and B² are significant model terms. Values above 0.1000 imply that the model terms are not significant. The final regression equation for the Ra model is presented in Equation 7 (in terms of actual factors).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Ra} = & -16.84523 \\
 & +1.85153 \text{ power} \\
 & -0.003174 \text{ Scanning speed} \\
 & -6.81068 \text{ laser line distance} \\
 & -0.000355 \text{ power * Scanning speed} \\
 & +0.030195 \text{ power * laser line distance} \\
 & -0.000359 \text{ Scanning speed * laser line distance} \\
 & -0.004048 \text{ power}^2 \\
 & +4.36585\text{E-}06 \text{ Scanning speed}^2 \\
 & +0.219485 \text{ laser line distance}^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Table 8: ANOVA for surface roughness (Ra).

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	11127.89	9	1236.43	25.34	0.0112	significant
A-power	1484.74	1	1484.74	30.43	0.0117	
B-Scanning speed	6770.46	1	6770.46	138.76	0.0013	
C-laser line distance	289.07	1	289.07	5.92	0.093	
AB	1019.52	1	1019.52	20.9	0.0196	
AC	36.47	1	36.47	0.7475	0.4509	
BC	65.25	1	65.25	1.34	0.3312	
A²	5.99	1	5.99	0.1228	0.7492	
B²	1116.58	1	1116.58	22.89	0.0174	
C²	68.82	1	68.82	1.41	0.3204	
Residual	146.37	3	48.79			
Cor Total	11274.26	12				

c) Machining Time

Table 9 presents the ANOVA results for Machining time. The model's F-value of 25.88 indicates that the model is statistically significant, with only a 0.35% probability that such a high F-value could arise from random variation. P-values below 0.0500 suggest that the corresponding model terms have a significant effect. In this analysis, the terms B, C, BC, and B² are identified as significant. Conversely, terms with P-values above 0.1000 are considered not significant. The final regression

equation for the Ra model is presented in Equation 8 (in terms of actual factors)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Machining Time} = & +7.56931 \\
 & +0.075857 \text{ power} \\
 & -0.003673 \text{ Scanning speed} \\
 & -0.302995 \text{ laser line distance} \\
 & +2.49965\text{E-}20 \text{ power * Scanning speed} \\
 & +1.12117\text{E-}17 \text{ power * laser line distance} \\
 & +0.000065 \text{ Scanning speed * laser line distance} \\
 & -0.000474 \text{ power}^2 \\
 & +3.20482\text{E-}07 \text{ Scanning speed}^2
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Table 9: ANOVA for Machining time.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	48.96	8	6.12	25.88	0.0035	significant
A-power	0.0000	1	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	
B-Scanning speed	34.99	1	34.99	147.91	0.0003	
C-laser line distance	3.03	1	3.03	12.82	0.0232	
AB	0.0000	1	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	
AC	0.0000	1	0.0000	0.0000	1.0000	
BC	2.17	1	2.17	9.16	0.0389	
A²	0.1007	1	0.1007	0.4257	0.5497	
B²	7.37	1	7.37	31.16	0.0051	
Residual	0.9461	4	0.2365			
Cor Total	49.91	12				

d) Lattice Strain

The ANOVA for lattice strain is shown in Table 10. The model is significant, as indicated by its F-value of 83.14. It's only a 1.19% chance that noise could cause an F-value of this magnitude. Model terms are considered significant when their p-values are below 0.0500. Here, AB, BC, B², and BC² are important terms in the model. If the value is higher than 0.1000, the model terms are not important. The final regression equation for the Ra model is presented in Equation 9 (in terms of actual factors)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Lattice strain} = & -0.250993 \\
 & +0.001881 \text{ power} \\
 & +0.000121 \text{ Scanning speed} \\
 & +0.056941 \text{ laser line distance} \\
 & -4.93519\text{E-}07 \text{ power * Scanning speed} \\
 & -0.000030 \text{ power * laser line distance} \\
 & -0.000016 \text{ Scanning speed * laser line distance} \\
 & +7.01265\text{E-}06 \text{ power}^2 \\
 & +6.84509\text{E-}09 \text{ Scanning speed}^2 \\
 & -0.001725 \text{ laser line distance}^2 \\
 & +4.79735\text{E-}07 \text{ Scanning speed * laser line distance}^2
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{9}$$

Table 10: ANOVA for lattice strain.

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	p-value	
Model	0.0169	10	0.0017	83.14	0.0119	significant
A-power	0.0046	1	0.0046	226.84	0.0044	
B-Scanning speed	0.0038	1	0.0038	186.05	0.0053	
C-laser line distance	0.0006	1	0.0006	27.21	0.0348	
AB	0.002	1	0.002	96.78	0.0102	
AC	0	1	0	1.72	0.3203	
BC	0.0014	1	0.0014	66.36	0.0147	
A²	0	1	0	0.8823	0.4467	
B²	0.0027	1	0.0027	134.65	0.0073	
C²	0.0002	1	0.0002	11.53	0.0769	
BC²	0.0015	1	0.0015	71.45	0.0137	
Residual	0	2	0			
Cor Total	0.017	12				

3.2. Statistical Interpretation of Perturbation Plots

The perturbation plots, as shown in Figure 3, illustrate the relative influence of three input parameters: laser power (A), laser scanning speed (B), and laser line distance (C). On four critical response variables: material removal rate (MRR), surface roughness (Ra), machining time, and lattice strain. Those are critical parameters for evaluating the performance of laser micro-machining, as they directly affect the quality of the micro-machining. The center point of each plot represents the reference (nominal) level of the variables, and deviations reflect the coded levels used in the experimental design [28].

For Material Removal Rate (MRR), the Laser power (A) and scanning speed (B) both show strong positive main effects on MRR. Increased power

supplies provide greater energy density, enhancing ablation efficiency, while higher scanning speeds allow greater surface coverage per unit time. The negligible slope of factor C (laser line distance) implies an insignificant main effect, confirmed by its flat response trend.

For Surface roughness (Ra), Higher scanning speeds reduce the interaction time between the laser and material, minimizing thermal damage and resulting in smoother surfaces. Conversely, higher laser power and wider line spacing (greater C) likely induce excessive localized heating and material re-deposition, increasing Ra.

For Machining time, a significant reduction in machining time with increased scanning speed is expected and statistically validated. The marginal increase in machining time with higher power and line distance may be due to secondary effects such as

heat accumulation and the need for post-processing or multiple passes. This implies that while B is a dominant predictor, the interaction terms (AB, BC) should also be evaluated for model accuracy

For Lattice strain, Higher scanning speeds reduce the thermal gradient and the associated residual stresses, thus decreasing lattice strain. In contrast,

elevated laser power increases local energy input, potentially inducing higher thermal stresses and associated lattice distortions. This aligns with typical thermomechanical modeling outcomes and could be statistically supported by significant coefficients in the fitted model and low standard error.

Figure 3. The perturbation plots for responses: Material Removal Rate (MRR), surface roughness (Ra), machining time, and lattice strain (A = laser power, B = scanning speed, C = laser line distance).

3.3. 3D Surface Plot Interpretation

The 3D response surface plots provide a deeper understanding of interaction and curvature effects used to evaluate the responses of Material Removal Rate (MRR), Surface Roughness (Ra), Machining Time, and Lattice Strain concerning laser power, laser scanning speed, and laser scanning distance [29]. As shown in Figure 4, the two most effective

parameters from Figure 3 are selected on the x and y axes for each response.

Material Removal Rate (MRR): The plot shows that MRR increases with higher laser power and lower scanning speed. This suggests that higher energy input with slower traversal enables more material to be removed per unit time, likely due to prolonged energy interaction with the substrate.

Surface Roughness (Ra): Ra increases sharply with higher laser power and lower scanning speed, indicating that excessive energy density leads to surface degradation or melting irregularities. Optimal surface finish is achieved at moderate power and higher scanning speeds, where thermal accumulation is minimized.

Machining Time: As expected, machining time increases significantly with slower scanning speeds and larger laser line distances. This reflects reduced processing efficiency at lower scan speeds and greater spacing between lines, both of which extend the time needed to cover the machining area.

Lattice Strain: Lattice strain is influenced by both scanning speed and laser power. Higher power and lower speed lead to increased strain, likely due to deeper thermal penetration and residual stress accumulation. Conversely, higher speeds and moderate power reduce strain by limiting heat-affected zones and allowing better thermal dissipation.

These plots confirm the complex, nonlinear interactions between parameters, emphasizing the need for precise optimization to balance material removal efficiency, surface integrity, and structural stability.

Figure 4. The surface plot is a three-dimensional graphical representation of responses: Material Removal Rate (MRR), surface roughness (Ra), machining time, and lattice strain.

3.4. Mathematical Model Validation: Predicted vs. Actual Response Analysis

To evaluate the predictive performance and reliability of the mathematical modeling developed using Response Surface Methodology (RSM), diagnostic plots were constructed. These plots compared the predicted (calculated) values to the actual experimental data for all four response variables [30].

Such diagnostic plots serve as essential tools in verifying the suitability and accuracy of the regression models. They provide visual confirmation of how closely the model aligns with real-world results [31].

Additionally, a probability graph was plotted as a hallmark of the model's significance. This graph offers a more insightful and revealing perspective on the model's effectiveness. Figure 5 illustrates the

responses gathered from 13 experiments conducted using a BBD. Notably, the data points lie close to the diagonal line, highlighting the feasibility and workability of the developed model.

The coefficient of correlation (R^2) plays a critical role in evaluating model accuracy following the optimization of the response surfaces and determination of the regression coefficients via the least squares method. A higher R^2 value indicates a stronger predictive capability. In this study, a strong agreement was observed between the predicted (calculated) values and experimental results across the response variables. The R^2 values for Material Removal Rate (MRR), Surface Roughness (Ra), Machining Time, and Lattice Strain were found to be 96.31%, 98.7%, 98.1%, and 99.76%, respectively, each significantly exceeding the commonly accepted threshold of 75%, thereby confirming the regression modeling high accuracy [32].

Figure 5. Plot of Predicted vs. Actual Response: Material Removal Rate (MRR), surface roughness (Ra), machining time, and lattice strain.

Furthermore, the adjusted R^2 values for the respective models were found to be 88.94% for MRR, 94.81% for Ra, 94.31% for Machining Time, and 98.56% for Lattice Strain, with the differences between adjusted and actual R^2 values remaining within 0.2, indicating model stability. Additionally, the model precision ratios calculated as 11.06 (MRR), 15.00 (Ra), 14.50 (Machining Time), and 36.41 (Lattice Strain) all surpassed the standard threshold value of 4, demonstrating a strong signal-to-noise ratio [32]. These outcomes collectively confirm the model's robustness and its effectiveness in accurately capturing the system behavior, thereby making it suitable for exploring and optimizing the design space.

3.5. Phase Constituents via X-ray Diffraction

As shown in Figure 6, the SS b unprocessed sample (3-mm 316L sheet) shows the canonical γ -Fe (FCC) pattern, dominant $\gamma(111) \approx 43.5^\circ$, $\gamma(200) \approx 50.7^\circ$, $\gamma(220) \approx 74.6^\circ$ —consistent with undeformed austenitic 316L. After CNC milling (SS M), γ peaks exhibit slight 2θ shifts and FWHM broadening from machining-induced residual stresses and elevated dislocation density in the surface layer detected by line-profile XRD analyses [33]. Where deformation is severe, small bcc α' -martensite reflections (e.g., $\approx 44.7^\circ$) may appear, as strain-induced martensite is

well documented in 316L under cold working or machining strains [34]. Across the laser-machined series SS 1–SS 13, γ -Fe remains dominant, but additional peaks near $\approx 30.2^\circ$, 35.6° , 57.2° , and 62.7° indicate spinel oxides ($\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4 / \gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) generated by laser heating and oxidation of 316-series steels [35]. The oxide-peak intensity generally scales with laser energy density, interaction time, and matching reports that higher power density forms denser iron-oxide scales [35]. For very rough surfaces (SS 3, SS 8–SS 10), diffracted intensities are suppressed at low angles and peaks broaden because facet misorientation or porosity and defocusing cause geometric, not purely microstructural, broadening [36]. Such roughness and local curvature complicate residual-stress quantification; grazing-incidence or surface smoothing is recommended to stabilize geometry and enhance surface-film detection [36]. Relative to SS b, both SS M and laser-machined samples often show larger γ -peak FWHM, attributable to microstrain and reduced coherent domain size in the affected layer (e.g. [33], [37]). Overall, the XRD differences reflect (i) deformation-driven effects from milling (residual stress, broadening, and occasional α'), and (ii) thermal-oxidative changes from laser micromachining modulated by surface roughness, in agreement with prior studies [34,35,37].

Figure 6. X-ray diffraction patterns for 13 samples of laser micro-machining with different conditions, in addition to an unprocessed sample (SS b), and a CNC milling-processed sample (SS M).

3.6. Residual stress analysis

Residual stresses in stainless steels can be effectively quantified by the X-ray diffraction (XRD) $\sin^2\psi$ method, which determines near-surface stress states from elastic lattice strain with high accuracy and without damaging the sample [38,39].

This technique remains the benchmark in machining and laser studies because peak shifts and broadening directly reflect the interplay of plastic deformation, thermal cycles, and microstructural changes [38,39]. Figure 7 shows the setup of X-ray diffraction (XRD) residual stress measurements.

The XRD normal-stress results for SS 316L across the base material SS b (unprocessed), CNC-milled, and laser-engraved conditions reproduce well-documented behavior. As shown in Figure 8, the untreated base material shows a near-compressive or low tensile surface state consistent with as-received 316L microstructure and rolling history. CNC milling produces pronounced tensile (or relieved compressive) normal stresses ($\approx 497\text{--}588$ MPa) driven by severe plastic deformation and tool-workpiece mechanics, matching machining studies that report surface stresses of several hundred MPa dependent on cutting parameters [40]. For the laser case, we focused on Sample 13, selected as the optimum laser-engraved specimen owing to its maximum material removal rate and superior surface finish; under these conditions, laser micro-

machining yields tensile-leaning normal stresses ($\approx 490\text{--}603$ MPa) with more angular scatter and elevated shear components, in agreement with reports that localized heating-cooling cycles produce near-surface tensile stresses sensitive to energy density and scan speed [41,42]. Unlike bulk laser processes (e.g., L-PBF), engraving produces shallower stress penetration but allows controllable localization of residual stress and finer surface integrity control. This confirms that laser machining, when optimized (as in Sample 13), not only matches milling in stress magnitude but offers superior flexibility for tuning stress distribution, making the inclusion of laser parameter effects essential in your mathematical model of laser-beam machining, which may be a focus in future research work.

Figure 7. Set-up of X-ray diffraction (XRD) residual stress measurements for different SS 316L sample conditions.

Figure 8. Angular distribution of residual normal stresses, a) Sample SS_Base (unprocessed), b) Sample SS_CNC Milling, c) Sample SS_Laser micro-machining

3. CONCLUSION

This study investigated the Fiber laser micromachining technology for stainless steel 316L material and aims to use input parameters using

response surface methodology (RSM) to enhance process efficiency (Material removal rate, machining time) and product quality (surface roughness, lattice strain), and overall performance according to

application. Most effective control parameters and their respective window were selected based on previous literature (laser power from 28.7 to 51.7 W), (laser scanning speed from 500 to 5000 mm/sec), and (laser line distance from 10 to 20 μm). The key findings include the following:

- The laser scanning speed (B) appears to be the most influential parameter across all responses, particularly in reducing surface roughness up to 7.515 μm measured by laser confocal microscope, machining time up to 0.365 minutes, and lattice strain up to 0.2465 % through XRD results.
- Laser power (A) significantly improves MRR up to 1.03093 mg/min, but can negatively affect surface roughness up to 95.162 μm and lattice strain up to 0.330667 %.
- Laser line distance (C) shows a limited impact across all responses, suggesting that its optimization window might be narrow or less sensitive in this process.
- These perturbation plots were observed to be consistent with the regression method through the RSM model, likely a second-order polynomial. The trends observed in the plots are consistent with statistically significant factors identified in the regression and ANOVA tables.
- These findings highlight the importance of balancing laser power and scanning speed to optimize productivity (MRR, machining time) and quality (Ra, lattice strain). The minimal effect of line distance may imply that it can be held constant or fine-tuned post-optimization.
- XRD analysis shows that CNC milling primarily induces peak broadening and occasional α' -martensite, confirming deformation-driven phase changes from plastic strain. By contrast, laser micromachining produces spinel oxide peaks alongside γ -Fe, demonstrating its ability to engineer both structural and chemical surface modifications through controlled thermal input.
- Residual stress measurements confirm that CNC milling generates tensile stresses from severe plastic deformation, consistent with prior machining studies. Optimized laser micromachining (Sample 13) achieves comparable stress magnitudes but with superior flexibility in stress localization and surface integrity tailoring, underscoring its advantage over conventional methods.

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4. DECLARATIONS

Ethical Approval: This declaration is not applicable.

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